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SERVICE AND ITS IMPROVEMENT IN DESERT PASTURE LIVESTOCK

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Abstract: The article substantiates the current state of the service system, ways of development and the need to introduce modern technologies, taking into account the characteristics of desert areas, as well as the need to organize industrial processing of livestock products on the ground.

Keywords: service, desert pasture areas, degradation, innovation, technology, processing, cost, revenue.

INTRODUCTION

Improving the forms of management in the desert-pasture areas, accelerating the use of innovative technologies in production, accelerating the socio-economic development of Karakul districts, taking into account the low level of production and market infrastructure in many respects. in particular, the volume of paid, commercial and domestic services.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The following scholars have considered service and its improvement in desert pasture livestock in their research: Kayumov F.K. [1], Ibragimov Yu. [2], Tangirov A.E. [3].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the implementation of the study, the conclusions and recommendations are formed as a result of the analysis of indicators of effective development of communication services through economic methods. In addition, the method of analysis and synthesis was used effectively in the conduct of scientific research.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Karakul is scattered over very large areas of the republic, a few of the cities and industrial centers 100 km. 56-58% of karakul sheep are raised on relatively small farms and produce 78-80% of the main crops, in particular, karakul skins, and the year-round grazing of desert-pastoral livestock and other peculiarities. it is necessary to form production services taking into account the requirements of a market economy.

Stabilization of production development in tea and pasture livestock, especially karakul, requires modernization of shepherd's houses, production facilities, water

sources and other facilities serving production, along with the introduction of technologies that prevent pasture degradation and dramatically increase productivity.

Construction of the following facilities for services provided by entrepreneurs or private entrepreneurs, depending on the size of the production departments of the karakul industry (herds, livestock complexes, farmers and farms):

Sheep bathing facility, sheep wool shearing station equipped with necessary machinery and equipment, artificial insemination point, laboratory for veterinary activities, shepherd's houses, open and closed barns, garage, feed shop and feed storage, water storage facility, Becker landfill (Figure 1). At the same time, farms specializing in the cultivation of seeds of desert-pasture plants, facilities for primary processing and processing of crops, in particular the slaughter of lambs, primary processing and processing and storage of astrakhan skin and wool, slaughter and processing of sheep, marri sheep milking and milk processing, construction of sheep and other cattle skin processing facilities on the ground. Electricity,

It is known that 1 ton of manure can be processed to produce 100 m³ of biogas, to collect 560-570 tons of manure per year from 2500 sheep and to produce 56000-57000 m³ of biogas. Part of it can be used as a gas fuel in shepherd's houses, as a fuel for vehicles, while the other part can be used to run generators to generate electricity. This, in turn, creates convenience for shepherds and other staff in everyday life, significantly reduces the cost of products and services, and allows for a smooth and uninterrupted workflow.

The analysis of the current state of economic activity shows that the number of sheep grazed on the herds of specialized farms does not exceed 500-600 heads. For example, in the Sahoba ota breeding farm, on average, 230 sheep are raised by 7%, 363 by 15.8, 470 by 37, 543 by 21, and 717 by 19%. The average number of sheep grazed in a herd is 499 heads. Farms have 206 heads - 66.2%, 411 heads - 22.5, 666 heads - 5 and 1200 and more heads - 6.3%.

In farms, the average number of sheep with 50 heads is 72.3%, 206 heads with 20.7 heads and those with 400 or more heads of sheep with 7.0%.

Based on these and the above-mentioned features of karakul sheep care, as well as in order to introduce new, advanced technologies, it is expedient to organize the production facilities in a stable and portable form.

The use of a mobile shepherd's house in the process of stable transfer of sheep from pasture to pasture, service facilities for farms and herds of specialized farms, which increased the number of sheep to 2500-3000 heads due to the introduction of innovative pastures, 2500-3000 heads for small farms and herds providing sheep

shearing, artificial insemination, slaughter of lambs for astrakhan skin, and organization of mobile laboratories and poultry houses are economically justified (Fig. 1).

Figure 1
Service facilities and their composition

In the desert and semi-desert regions, the opportunities for desert-pastoral livestock are wide, but the economic conditions for the development of other industries are almost non-existent. Given the natural, technological, organizational and economic characteristics of the industry, the development of rural industry here is both an economic and a social advantage. In these regions it is expedient to organize the production of mixed fodder, processing of feed, astrakhan and cattle skins, meat, wool and milk. In addition, it is necessary to create service points for the population and production. A group of scientists have identified such enterprises and organizations as corporate property, that is, the accumulation of investment funds of desert-pastoral farms, the establishment of inter-farm organizations and the development of small business. while the second group of economists recommend the development of agriculture in a market economy only on the basis of vertical cooperation. At the same time, “agricultural producers should establish economic relations not only with producers, but also with processors, processors, traders, intermediaries, service organizations and work closely with them.”(2).In our opinion, in order to ensure sustainable socio-economic development of the regions with desert livestock, it is expedient to create a single economic entity through the integration of production, processing, sales, cultural, household and production services. .

It was noted that the processing and delivery of products grown by desert-pastoral livestock to consumers is one of the unresolved problems. Lack of processing capacity of most of the products, almost no use of products such as sheep's milk, hides and wool, and the organization of local processing of raw materials in order to accelerate the socio-economic development of the regions and bring the welfare of the desert population to the level of cities economic, social system.

The organization of on-site processing of cattle skins will also lead to the industrialization of the village and increase the welfare of the rural population through the development of infrastructure and the creation of additional jobs, while ensuring sustainable development.

V. CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

According to the results of research:

1. To ensure sustainable socio-economic development of the regions with desert and pasture livestock, we propose to create a unified economic organism through the integration of production, processing, sales, cultural, household services and production services, ie as a sub-complex ;

2. It is possible to process 100 tons of biogas per ton of manure, collect 560-570 tons of manure per year from 2500 sheep and produce 56000-57000m³ of biogas. Organization of biogas production;

3. Stable and portable organization of production facilities for the introduction of new, advanced technologies;

4. We propose to develop infrastructure and create additional jobs through the organization of on-site processing of products.

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